

Path coefficient analysis showing direct and indirect effects of different fractions of soil Zn on rice plant uptake.

Variable	Water-soluble Zn	Exchangeable Zn	Complexed Zn	Organic Zn	Amorphous sesquioxide Zn	Crystalline sesquioxide Zn	Residual Zn	Correlation with Zn uptake <i>r</i>
Water-soluble Zn	0.0094 ^a	0.0034	-0.0001	0.0009	0.0024	-0.0020	-	-0.1463
Exchangeable Zn	-0.2453	-0.6738 ^a	-0.465	-0.0510	-0.4770	-0.0389	0.1709	-0.0656
Complexed Zn	-0.0146	0.9136	1.3238 ^a	0.5479	0.9396	0.1861	-0.8276	-0.0091
Organic Zn	-0.0556	-0.0425	-0.2323	-0.5612 ^a	-0.1354	0.0423	0.1923	-0.2877
Amorphous sesquioxide Zn	-0.0054	-0.0149	-0.0149	-0.0051	-0.0210 ^a	-0.0038	0.0047	-0.0209
Crystalline sesquioxide Zn	0.1693	-0.0462	-0.1125	0.0603	-0.1463	-0.8000 ^a	-0.3668	-0.2437
Residual Zn	-0.0042	-0.2054	-0.5081	-0.2795	-0.1833	0.3727	0.8129 ^a	-0.0136

^aDirect effects. All other effects are indirect.

fied by Mandal and Mandal. Much of the native Zn (46.2-84.5%) was in the residual mineral fraction. That fraction contributed very little to plant uptake.

The water-soluble, exchangeable, complexed, and organically bound fractions were the most important; content in the different soils ranged from 0.044 to 0.8, 0.073 to 1.2, 1.71 to

16.4, and 1.25 to 26.43% in different soils. Amorphous and crystalline sesquioxide-bound Zn ranged from 2.03 to 8.91 and 1.86 to 5.12%, respectively.

Path coefficient analysis was used to identify the relative contribution of different fractions to Zn uptake by rice. Values were highest for the complexed

Zn (1.324), followed by that for residual Zn (0.813) (see table). The other fractions showed no dominant effect on Zn uptake. The overall negative correlations of all fractions with Zn uptake indicate that native soil Zn fractionation values after incubation with applied Zn would be more useful to predict Zn uptake by rice. □

Crop management

Response of rice to applied P in soils of different P status

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We conducted a 2-yr greenhouse experiment to study the response of rice to fertilizer P on soils of different agroclimatic regions of Punjab. Soils varied in available P (Olsen extractable) from low (1.72 ppm) to high (39.20 ppm) and in texture from loamy sand to silty clay loam.

P was applied as monoammonium phosphate at 0, 6.6, 13.2, 19.8, and 26.4 ppm P to 7 kg soil in polyethylene-lined 10-kg enamel pots. Recommended N, K, and Zn were applied. PR106 raised in sand culture was transplanted 35 d after seeding at 4 hills/pot and 2 plants/hill. Water level was maintained at 2 cm throughout.

Applied P significantly increased yield both years in soils testing low and medium in available P (see table). Rice in soils high in available P did not respond to applied P. Seven of 8 low-P

soils and 3 of 5 medium-P soils responded significantly to fertilizer P the first year; 8 of 9 low-P soils and 6 of 11 medium-P soils responded significantly to P the second year.

P removal by the rice crop ranged from an average 60 mg/pot in low-P soils to 119 mg/pot in high-P soils (see

table). The increase in P uptake with increased applied P was significant up to 19.8 ppm P in low-P soils and 6.6 ppm P in medium-P soils the first year and up to 19.8 ppm P in both low- and medium-P soils the second year. Differences in P uptake in high-P soils were not significant either year. □

Effect of P level on rice yields and P uptake in soils with different levels (0-26.4ppm) of available P. Punjab, India.

Available P	Year	0	6.6 ppm	13.2 ppm	19.8 ppm	26.4 ppm	LSD (0.05)
<i>Rice yield (g/pot)</i>							
Low	1	20.2	25.0	28.4	28.4	28.7	1.5
	2	14.6	28.0	34.6	36.6	-	1.7
	Mean	18.4	26.5	31.5	32.5	-	
Medium	1	26.0	29.4	32.5	31.2	30.0	1.7
	2	30.4	36.2	38.9	39.5	-	1.4
	Mean	29.2	32.8	35.7	35.4	-	
High	1	30.5	30.4	30.8	30.4	30.6	ns
	2	36.9	37.4	36.7	37.7	-	ns
	Mean	33.7	33.7	33.8	34.1	-	
<i>P uptake (mg/pot)</i>							
Low	1	60.0	80.9	76.6	100.8	93.4	5.6
	2	42.3	63.4	83.9	93.5	-	5.6
	Mean	51.2	77.2	79.9	97.1	-	
Medium	1	85.6	95.5	99.8	107.2	111.6	4.8
	2	91.7	106.2	117.3	127.6	-	3.9
	Mean	88.6	98.8	108.8	117.4	-	
High	1	98.3	98.8	102.7	105.3	106.6	7.1
	2	119.0	122.3	124.4	122.6	-	ns
	Mean	108.6	110.5	113.5	114.5	-	